

The Women Empowerment in India

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Introduction

Women Empowerment is a significant topic of discussion, mainly in undersized and developing nations. They have lately realized that the development that they aspire cannot be achieved unless we achieve gender equality by empowering the women. Economic empowerment of the women denotes to their right to control the economic decisions, income, assets and other equivalents by improving their economic as well as the social status.

Women Empowerment

Women Empowerment means promoting the women in their social and the economic development by providing them equal opportunities of the employment, education, economic development and allowing them to socialize the freedoms and rights that were denied before. The process which empowers the women to know that they too can achieve their aspirations as the men of the society and help them to do that

Need for Women's Empowerment in India

The status of Indian women has declined from the ancient period to the medieval period. Though in the modern era Indian women have held the significant political and administrative posts still, on the contrary, there is a majority of the rural women who are confined to their homes and don't have the access to fulfil basic health amenities and education.

The female literacy rate in India lags behind the male literacy rate by a significant ratio. Literacy rate for men in India is 81.3% and that of the women is 60.6%. Many Indian girls don't have access to the school and even if they do, they are falling out during the early years. Only 29% of the Indian young women have completed ten or more years of then education.

Low education rate among the women has kept them away from the main workforce by resulting in their social and economical corrosion. Women in urban areas are well employed than their village counterparts; nearly 30% of employees in the Indian software

industry to constitute the women. On the contrary, nearly 90% of rural women are employed as daily wage labour, mainly in the agriculture and allied sectors. Next factor brings in the need for the woman empowerment in India is paying disparity. Women in India are not being paid equivalent to their male counterparts in various sectors. According to the study women in India with the same years of experience and qualification are paid 20% less than their male counterparts having the same credentials. She is just a few days away from entering into the new year 2019, India is occupied with the hope and aspirations as never before and she is about to win back her tag of world's fastest-growing economy. We will achieve it soon, but could only maintain it, if we remove the problems of the gender inequality by giving equal opportunities for the employment, development and wages to our men and women alike.

Barriers to Women Empowerment

Indian society is a compound society with varied customs, rituals, beliefs and traditions. Sometimes these age-old beliefs and customs constitute the most significant barriers to the empowerment of women in India. Few of the significant barriers to the women empowerment in India are explained below-

1) Social Norms

Many societies in India restrict women from leaving the house for having given to their orthodox belief and the age-old traditions. Women in such societies are not allowed to go outside either for education or for the employment and forced to live an isolated and dejected life. Women living under such conditions to become accustomed by being inferior to the men and are unable to change their present social and economic status.

2) Workplace Sexual Harassment

Workplace sexual harassment is the most significant barrier to women empowerment in India. Private sectors like the hospitality industry, software industry, educational institutions and hospitals are some of the worst affected areas. It is a manifestation of deep-rooted male supremacy in society. There had been a steep rise of about 170% in the workplace sexual harassment of women in India in the past couple of decades.

3) Gender Discrimination

Majority of the women in India still meet gender discrimination at the workplace as well as in society. Societies don't permit women to go out for employment or education. They are not allowed to take the independent decisions either for their work or for family and they are treated inferior to the men. Such discrimination of the women leads to their socio-economic decline and hugely contradicts the "Woman Empowerment".

4) Pay Disparity

Women in India are paid less than their male counterparts. The situation is worst in unorganized sectors where women are employed as daily wage labour. Women who are working for the same number of the hours and doing the same work are paid less than the men which imply unequal powers between the men and the women. Even the women who are employed in an organized sector are paid less than their male counterparts for having the equivalent qualification and then experience.

5) Illiteracy

Female illiteracy and their high dropout rate are one of the major obstacles to the empowerment of the women in India. In urban India, girls are at lower when we compare with boys in terms of education but they significantly lack behind in the rural areas. The effective literacy rate of women is 64.6%, while that of the men is 80.9%. A lot of the Indian girls who join in the school, dropout in the initial years without having passed even 10th grade.

6) Child Marriage

India has successfully reduced child marriages in the past few decades, through several laws and initiatives taken by the government still a report in early 2018 by the UNICEF (United Nations Children Emergency Fund) states that nearly 1.5 Million girls in India get married before they turn 18. Early marriage reduces the growth prospects of the girls who soon be moving into adulthood.

7) Crimes against the Women

The Indian women have been subjected to domestic violence and other crimes such as – dowry, honour killing and trafficking. Strangely, women in urban areas are more prone to criminal assault than women in rural areas. Even the working women in big cities avoid using public transport in late hours for fearing their modesty and life. Woman empowerment can only be achieved in the true sense if we ensure the safety of our women by providing them with the liberty to roam easily without fear as the men in the society do.

8) Female Infanticide

The Female infanticide or sex-selective abortion is also one of the major obstacles to the woman empowerment in India. Female infanticide means identifying the gender of the fetus and aborting it when it is exposed to be a female often without the mother's consent. The Female infanticide has led to a high male-female sex ratio in the states of the Haryana and the Jammu and Kashmir. Our dues on the woman empowerment will not be substantiated unless we eradicate the female infanticide or sex-selective abortion.

Government's Role in the Woman Empowerment in India

The government of India has implemented many programs for the empowerment of women. Many of these programs are for providing the employment, education and health accessible to the masses. These programs have been specially incorporated keeping in mind the needs and the conditions of Indian women to ensure their participation. Some of these programs are – MNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme), Sarva Siksha Abhiyaan, Janani Suraksha Yojana (reduce maternal mortality).

The Ministry of Women and Child Development, The Government of India has implemented various new schemes specifically aimed at the empowerment of the Indian women. Some of those significant schemes are given below-

1) Beti Bachao Beti Padhao Scheme

This scheme focuses on eradicating the female infanticide and also on the education of the girl child. It aims for changing the mindset of the people towards a girl, by providing financial support and also by strict enforcement of the laws and acts.

2) Women Helpline Scheme

This scheme aims to provide 24 hours emergency to support helpline for the women who are subjected to any kind of violence or the crime. This scheme provides a universal emergency number -181 across the country for the women in distress. A number also provides information on the women related schemes in the country.

3) Ujjawala Scheme

This scheme aim at the rescue of the women affected by trafficking and the commercial sexual exploitation their rehabilitation and social welfare.

4) Support to Training and Employment Programme for the Women (STEP)

The STEP scheme aims at imparting skills to the women by making them employable as well as to become self-employed. Various sectors like agriculture, horticulture, handloom, tailoring and fisheries are covered under these schemes.

5) Mahila Shakti Kendras

This scheme focuses on empowering rural women through their community participation. Community volunteers like students and professionals will teach rural women about their rights and welfare schemes.

6) Reservation for Women in the Panchayati Raj Institutions

In 2009 the Union Cabinet of the Government of India instituted 50% of the reservation for the women in the Panchayati Raj Institutions. It is aimed mainly at improving the social status of women in rural India. The states of Bihar, Jharkhand, Orissa, and Andhra Pradesh among various others have the majority of the women as elected the head of the gram panchayats.

Conclusion

We must understand that the women empowerment is a process which hopes to bring gender equality and a balanced economy. The Indian women had been President, Prime ministers, civil servants, doctors and lawyers. but still, a good majority of them needs to help and support. Support to be educated, to do what they want to do, to travel safe, to work safely and to be independent for making their own decisions. The way to the socio-economic development of India goes through the socio-economic development of the womenfolk.

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